

PROSTITUTION: A QUALITATIVE STUDY OF THE PERCEPTUAL VIEWS AND PSYCHOLOGICAL STRUGGLES ON THE LIVES OF FEMALE SEX-WORKERS

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Prostitution: A Qualitative Study of the Perceptual Views and Psychological Struggles on the Lives of Female Sex-Workers

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Abstract

Having a noble livelihood is one of the majority's wishes, but there are souls stuck in the mud and poverty. This includes paid women who are willing to take risks and face the scorn of others just to sell sexual services in exchange for money. This qualitative research gave a voice to women in the field of prostitution to reveal their perspective and psychological struggle in their occupation. The data in this research came from interviews with female sex workers from Metro Manila. The obtained information was analyzed through thematic analysis. Based on the research results, the main themes were developed and extended: poverty, clinging to the knife, life's blows, living despite the humiliation, faith, and new hope. Despite the negative connotations, it can be seen that hope has sprouted in their feelings. There is hope that, in time, they will be able to get out of their misery. Apart from this, it is also undeniable that their faith and prayer in the Above remained with them even though life with a heavy burden was associated with it.

Keywords: *prostitution, perceptual views, psychological struggles*

Introduction

Most of the citizens today are stuck in the hardships of life. This may be due to the lack of job opportunities or education, or it may also result from the lack of economic opportunities. Many want to get out of poverty and earn money, but due to a lack of education, they are forced to engage in unpleasant activities such as selling entertainment or prostitution. The sale of entertainment is rampant in major cities such as Manila and Makita, as well as in various provinces throughout the Philippines. This is one of the oldest professions; even in the time before Christ, there was a worker. In other religions, having sex with priests is a way to get closer to their worshiped god, and it is done in rituals to make a woman or man sterile.

In the psychological aspect, this research was done better to understand the views and struggles of paid women. The researchers wanted to better understand the feelings of a woman who chose to stick to the knife and sell flesh despite the possible social scorn and danger it could cause. This study seeks to answer the following questions: in what way did women end up in this type of life; how do describe the feelings of the participants when they entered this lifestyle; how are they able to continue this work and what are the possible destinies and life plans of women in this line of work? This research aims to discover the emotional views of paid women and present their various situations and adventures in the field of their occupation. This study also presents the reflection of a wage-earning woman's work and how they manage to go about their lives.

Literature Review

In order to extend the knowledge about the emotional views of prostitutes and prostitution, the following literature presents various research about the following: the initiation of the carnal trend or the prevalence of prostitution, the expansion of prostitution in various forms of commercialism, the reasons why women fall into prostitution, the experiences and effects of prostitution on prostitutes, and the transformations of prostitutes after leaving prostitution.

The following discussion describes the definition of prostitution. According to Scoular and O'Neill (2017), prostitution is a victimless crime. It is re-evaluated as a crime that threatens the women and children involved and threatens to destroy individuals, families, and communities.

Alanazi (2017) proved that in the past centuries, women were made to be only the shadow of men, and society suppressed the rights of women. In addition to this, women, in the changing times, did not have a voice for their sexuality. Alanazi (2017) also stated that women view the lack of freedom because of weaknesses in the patriarchal society. Society gives people more power to make decisions on behalf of women including how they should live their lives.

Abiera and Lalusis (2018) added sexual tourism involves a relationship between prostitution and tourism. Also, the production and consumption of this type of service have been local and global for a long time. In addition, the form of the sex tourism industry is the same as tourism itself in general. Tourists request what the country has established, while service providers suggest where they think tourists are interested (Abiera & Lalusis, 2018). Sex tourism, on the other hand, occurs when tourists visit a particular country or area to engage in sexual activity, usually with residents who provide sexual services. According to them, the Philippines, like other countries in Southeast Asia, has a reputation for prostitution and sexuality tourism.

This literature discussion is about the reasons why women fall into prostitution. Also, according to Abiera and Lalusis (2018), sex workers work as waitresses, dancers, singers, or "guest relations officers" in the clubs and bars where they join with the client paying

an additional fee. Also, there are workers called "freelancers"; they are sexual service providers who come from independent bars and look for customers who agree to pay for their time.

According to Alanazi (2017), contrary to what other research says, Sex pimping is an option for women whose desire is to achieve financial independence. Alanazi (2017) adds that research has shown that the motivations of migrant sex workers are varied and often cannot be clearly divided into voluntary and forced. It helps him as a sex worker to have a better understanding of his sexual identity because later he can enjoy sex with his clients (Alanazi, 2017).

According to Dubai, Sheridan, and Hopkins (2018), while structural factors primarily serve to establish a necessary level of financial security for women, the latter two speak more directly to the social and psychological standpoint of exit. The fourth discussion of the literature is about the experiences and effects of prostitution on hired women. In research by Anasti (2022), attention was paid to the contact of prostitutes with social workers to advocate for their human rights. There were interviews with 63 prostitutes and 10 social workers in the mid-western United States. According to the data obtained, most social workers support the decriminalization of this type of occupation, but their ability to make their support public is challenged.

Methodology

This research used a qualitative research method. This is also called qualitative research and aims to observe and record observations of the behavior of those who participate in their experience of the subject or purpose of the analysis (Jadaone, 2015). It was used by researchers to further analyze, understand, and explain the issue of prostitution and the emotional perspective and psychological interaction of prostitutes.

The participants in this study were six wage earners who were currently working as wage earners. Their ages range from 24 years old to 48 years old. The participants are from greater Manila. They work as prostitutes to support themselves and their families. This is by providing temporary happiness and comfort to their patrons in exchange for a set amount.

The data or information from the participants was gathered through interviews. This type of interview is slightly outlined. This is a research method where questions may be prepared for the interview, but the flow still depends on the depth of the discussion between the participant and the researcher (de Leon et al., 2018). It will be set at a date and place agreed upon by the researcher and participant. Each participant will be asked for permission for their participation in the interview.

Their consent corresponds to the signing of the consent letter for the participants. The researchers used an interview guide as a data collection instrument. It is divided into two subdivisions: a) demographic information of each participant and b) questions based on the presentation of the research problem. The data or information was analyzed through thematic analysis or coding. This is how the data will be broken down and allocated to each category in which they will be related and classified.

Results and Discussion

This section contains the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the qualitative data gathered from participant interviews. This includes presenting the answers along with their evaluations.

Table 1. Summary of Themes

Main Them	Sub-Theme 1	Sub-Theme 2	Sub-Theme 3	Sub-Theme 4
Tema 1: Poverty	<i>Isang Kahig, Isang Tuka</i>	<i>Walang-wala</i>	Lack in Education	
Tema 2: <i>Kapit sa Patalim</i>	Physical Abuse	<i>Pangamba</i>	Abuse	Threatening
Tema 3: Challenges in Life	<i>Kawalan ng Pag-asa</i>	Hatred	Sorrow	
Tema 4: <i>Pamumuhay sa kabila ng pang-aalipusta</i>	<i>Buhay ko ito</i>	<i>Sariling Diskarte</i>	<i>Bingi-bingihan sa sabi ng iba</i>	<i>Kapal ng Mukha</i>
Tema 5: Faith	Prayers	Repentance	<i>Kakampi ang Diyos</i>	
Tema 6: Hope	<i>Libre ang mangarap</i>	Plan for Self and Family	<i>Liwanag sa Kabila ng Kadiliman</i>	<i>Makaahon sa Pagkakasadlak</i>

Theme 1. Poverty

The difficulty of life was one of the main reasons given by the participants for entering this lifestyle. This includes the lack of education because the parents do not have the ability to study in school and the lack of daily food supply and livelihood. Although it was against their will to sell their bodies, they were left with no other choice.

In this work of prostitution, most of the women belong to the family who barely make ends meet by selling their bodies. They do it so they can survive. According to Delos Reyes (2018), most are used to a table or a beak. It is a state of life where one experiences poverty in life. Others are forced to gamble whatever they have to earn a living, such as hired women.

Walang-wala

According to the participants of this research, entering prostitution was their solution to the extreme poverty of life. At the point where even, their parents have nothing to support them, selling flesh became their option.

Salat sa Edukasyon

In life where education is not achieved, the situation is likely to be bitter. This is what happened to paid women who are called "pokpok". Because they did not finish school, finding decent jobs became difficult. Based on an article by Lacorte (2018), Filipinos having a proper education can be the key to the desired success in life, but not everyone has the opportunity to study for various reasons. Failure to graduate may result in a disadvantage when it comes to finding a job. According to him, it is rare to get a decent job without finishing school and others may try jobs such as prostitution.

Theme 2: Kapit sa Patalim

From the previous theme difficulty in life, it can be said that most of the participants in this research have experienced difficulty in life. This motivated them to make a daring decision so that they could survive. But their chosen livelihood is risky because it can also be the wick of their lives. This can also be the root of physical harm and abuse to them.

Physical Abuse

Despite the sexual service that prostitutes provide to their patrons, there are times when they experience excess and audacity. One is the physical pain they face in this job. There are people who are deliberately aggressive and violent and there are times when they don't deal with it immediately, which is why they end up in tragic events.

Apprehension

Physical assaults on prostitutes were not a joke experience that filled them with fear. It is fear for their lives and safety. Here are their stories from their real experiences at work,

K2: "*Alanganin, natatakot. Lalo ' pag sa bahay ka dinadala.*"

K4: "*Pero ano... nakakatakot din naman... kasi minsan may nakakahawak sa amin na warfreak... ganun..*" Abuse

Abuse is the unjust treatment of another person (PNU, 2020). In the standard of living of a mercenary woman it is not far that they experienced abuse. Despite these circumstances, they still do not have a voice to do justice to the abuse against them.

Participating paid women disclosed the abuses they experienced:

K1: "*Wala... wala siguro sya... Wala siyang pangbayad. Tinutukan ako ng baril kala ko papatayin ako eh (tumawa ng bahagya).*" K3: "*Meron. Di ka babayaran matapos gamitin ka. Tatakbuhan. Alanganin. Sila pa yung nag-aalanganin na takbuhan, yun pala sila yung tatakbo.*" (Tumatawa)

Threatening

Women do not mind paying for the dangers they have gone through in connection with their work. This includes threats to their lives. According to interviews with them, they are the only ones who avoid the dangers and threats that can be made to them especially and they do not know their patrons thoroughly.

Here are some of the threats to their lives that they have experienced, K3:

"*Uhum. Tutukan ka ng icepick tapos di ka pa babayaran.*"

K3: "*Hindi mo matatakas, may nakatutok sayong patalim.*"

In the analysis of these experiences, it can really be reflected that their work is associated with clinging to the knife. But they have no other choice or option because this is where they make a living.

Theme 3: Dagok sa Buhay

Instead of the work that makes a living for the paid women, there are various negative emotions. With every piece of money they earn there is a corresponding blow to their personality and emotions. Most of the time, it is their decision to enter this field, which is not hidden from others. Their bitter fate symbolizes despair, self-loathing, and grief.

Despair

Their floundering in the mud produced despair. It seems like a nightmare that cannot be erased from their being. Even if they want to get up and start over, their experiences remain imprinted.

K3: "*Wala, iiyak lang. Tapos sa isang gilid, yun magmumukmok sa isang gilid. Syempre. Parang sabihin mo na lang sa sarili mo gusto mo na lang mamatay. Parang ganun.*"

Even if they want to change their lives, they can't help but think that no one will accept them because of their experience as a comfort woman. There are also times when the answer they think of is death.

Hatred

Selling the body is an immoral act. As painful as this fact is, it is still part of the reality of the lives of prostitutes. They know about themselves and can't help but feel self-loathing.

K4: *"Ano lang... parang... Hindi ko alam eh... parang ano lang ba... Parang diring-diri ako sa sariliko ganun..."*

They also have the realization that using their bodies sexually to earn money is not normal work.

K4: *"Hindi... hindi ayoko naman din sa ganito... ang sagwa. Mas maganda po talaga 'yung magandang trabaho."*

K6: *"Yung mga... 'yung mga hindi ganito syempre... 'yung sa mga canteen lang ganun... 'yung normal ang kita... ganun... 'yung hindi ka gagamit ng katawan mo ganun."* (patuloy sa pag-iyak)

Sorrow

Emotionally, the work they entered brought them grief or great sadness. They are also human beings who also have hurt feelings. In times when other people hurt them and they can't do anything, they can only express their feelings through tears.

K3: *"Syempre masasaktan ka na lang, 'di ba? Wala, basta tahimik lang ako."*

K5: *"Mahirap para sa sarili kasi makikipagtalik ka sa iba'tibang tao."*

Theme 4: Pamumuhay sa Kabila ng Pang-aalipusta

Being labeled as a prostitute is a label that will tarnish the character of the participants. But this is the truth, and they can't deny it, these prostitutes don't seem to care what other people say. The reason is that they are not the ones who feed them.

"Buhay ko Ito"

Some of the paid female participants expressed the belief that it is their own life and that whatever they do is their own decision.

K1: *"Wala akong pakialam sa kanila. 'Di ko naman siguro sila naapektuhan sa ginagawa ko, buhay ko naman inaano ko 'di naman kanila eh. Oo may ganun ho talaga, wala naman akong magagawa kung anong tingin nila sa akin, wala akong pakialam sa sasabihin nila sa akin basta ako alam ko ang ginagawa ko."*

Own Strategy

Working as prostitute is considered their own strategy especially and they have a family that depends on them. According to them, this job is their way to survive. Many people criticize but they are not able to revive them. That's why they continue in the way they know.

Bingi-bingihan sa Sabi ng Iba

People around them always have something to say, even about things that are beyond their control. Often these criticisms are put in one ear and out the other. If they react to every harsh word that is thrown at them it may only make it more difficult for them. They may also be numb to other people's comments, so they seem to be turning a deaf ear.

Kapal ng Mukha

It is not unknown to everyone that working as a prostitute requires courage and guts. This will reach the point where the face will be thick enough to stomach the dirty work as part of their job.

Theme 5: Faith

Faith knows no one, even sinners, has the right to worship and ask for forgiveness. In this research, other people's judgments came out but did not become an obstacle for them to believe in God. It is said in the bible, "But they asked again and again, so Jesus stood up and said to them, "He who is without sin among you, let him be the first to throw a stone at him." (The New Testament: Filipino Standard Version, 2009, John 8:7).

Prayers

During the trials associated with their work, the participants still do not forget to pray. For them, their work does not reflect being a bad person.

K2: *"Talagang inaano ko... Sinasabi ko kay Lord na hindi naman ako masama. Wala naman akong inaanong tao. Wala, parang ano din sya sa akin. Dahil marami na rin nangyari dito na na-NBI to, itong mga pokpok dito."*

Repentance

Based on the interview with the participating prostitutes, there are times when they regret the life they have led. They admit to themselves that during the times they were given the opportunity to study they neglected and did not graduate until they ended up in this type of work.

K1: *"Oo (malungkot na boses). Oo parang ayaw ko na ng ganito. Sana nag-aral na lang ako. Sana hindi ko na ginawa 'to (tumawa ng bahagya).*

They also have attached a reminder to those who wish to enter this type of work. This is from their own experience that they still regret to this day.

K4: *“Kung papasukin nila ito, ‘wag na lang kasi, kasi ewan ko kasi sa akin talaga hindi, hindi magandang trabaho talaga ‘yung ganito. Hanggang ngayon pinagsisisihan kong ganitong trabaho pero wala eh. Pero hanggang sa ano.. hindi ako gumagawa ng katarantaduhan.. hindi lang din ako makulong.”*

Kakampi ang Diyos

Their faith in God will also be reflected in the protection of them from calamities. They believe that, somehow, the Lord still guides them and does not leave them in danger. Being a paid woman is not an obstacle for them to believe that there is a God who is on their side. Despite the suffering, bitterness and danger in the small world they live in, a whore's faith is one of their qualities to be reckoned with.

Theme 6: Bagong Pagasa

Everyone has the right to dream of a good life for the future, whether for themselves or the family. Regardless of what the participating women in this research have gone through, it can be said that they all have a dream of having a new chance in life.

Libre ang Mangarap

There is nothing wrong with dreaming, especially if it is for self-development. Even if it cannot be granted in the present, this will inspire them to look to the future with a strong desire to get out of the situation they are stuck in. According to them, if there is an opportunity, they will not waste it. They also dream that if there is a man who will accept them and be able to raise them. Nothing is impossible for a person with a dream; only time can tell where their lives lead.

Plan for Self

With simple plans, the first steps are to work hard. It may be simple for others, but for a poor woman, having a dignified job is a big life-changing thing.

K4: *“Gusto ko kasing magtinda ng inihaw... ganun.”*

K5: *“Magkaroon sana ng tindahan.”*

K6: *“Yung normal na buhay... ‘yung normal na trabaho..” Liwanag*

sa Kabila ng Kadiliman

Despite the darkness, the participants can still see the light of hope. This includes the money they hope to use to start a new life again. One of the participants hopes that through housing in PAGIBIG, he and his family can leave the place they are stuck in and change their lives.

Makaahon sa Pagkakasadlak

It is not too late, many of the prostitutes dream of getting out of their misery. It is for themselves and for their family. For them, having a quiet life, away from the abusive world and judgmental eyes of people is a taste of great comfort to them.

K2: *“Gusto kong magtrabaho ng maayos. Para sa mga anak ko kasi maglalakihan na yung mga anak ko. Mag-aaral na rin ‘yun eh.*

K5: *“Yung maging tahimik lang ang buhay ko... ‘yung makasama ko lang ang pamilya ko..”*

Even though there is a trace of hardship in their way of life, they do not lose hope. They wish that there is still a good future waiting for them and for their family.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the gathered information in the study, the following are the conclusions of the researchers. The research on the emotional perspective of prostitutes reflects the difficulty of life and depends on working in prostitution. Having the view that being a paid girl is the easiest way to make money and disregarding one's safety. Based on the collected views of poor women, what they have been hit by in life is presented in the following: (a) having hopelessness in life, (b) diminishing one's personality, (c) sacrificing oneself for when the family comes out, (d) formulating a plan and dream to get out of the chaos of life. The desire to get out of the fate of life as a paid woman while planning a new lifestyle is also included in their dreams for their future.

With the study's shared results and implications, the following recommendations are suggested: aiming to improve the mentality and perspective of a poor woman by rebuilding herself and turning away from the old lifestyle. The beginning of a new life by providing a new opportunity and order in the family situation that can be provided to them by government agencies such as the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD). The researchers also suggest further expanding the awareness of women in the country

regarding being paid women and emphasizing the possible dangers it can cause not only to the personality but also to the health of the body and mentality. Another recommendation is to strengthen the protection of the rights and welfare of women, especially women who end up in this trend of selling flesh. The last one is the continuation of deeper research regarding the mentality of women who are stuck in being paid women and having a link to ensure a renewed life after they abandon this lifestyle.

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